

Hotel Management System

Consider an hotel management system. The client accesses the system through the internet, and can book an hotel room, by choosing both check-in and check-out dates. The dates availability are verified and the reservation is confirmed and stored, if the selected dates are available. When booking a room in that hotel, the client needs to provide his/hers personal details.

Please specify an iStar 2.0 goal model describing this scenario, by using the tool on the right. When you finish, click on the button below.

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